

Neoleptonidae (Bivalvia) from Namibia

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urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:C7EA3309-95C7-4EA4-983C-86DB70E28B26

Recibido el 29-II-2024. Aceptado el 13-V-2024

ABSTRACT

This work presents two new species of the family Neoleptonidae (Bivalvia) found off Namibia, SW Africa: *Neolepton torraense* n. sp. and *Neolepton san* n. sp. *Neolepton torraense* n. sp. was found in a gravity core penetrating a Late Pleistocene stratigraphic sequence on the shelf and *Neolepton san* n. sp. was found alive on the upper bathyal slope. These records are the first of this genus off Namibia. We compare the two species found with, among others, *Neolepton atlanticum* (E. A. Smith, 1890), which is widespread in South Africa, on the basis of our own material from False Bay.

RESUMEN

Este trabajo presenta dos nuevas especies de la familia Neoleptonidae (Bivalvia) encontradas en Namibia, suroeste de África: *Neolepton torraense* n. sp. y *Neolepton san* n. sp. *Neolepton torraense* n. sp. se encontró en un testigo de gravedad que penetró una secuencia estratigráfica del Pleistoceno tardío en la plataforma y *Neolepton san* n. sp. fue encontrado vivo en el talud batial superior. Estos registros son los primeros de este género en aguas frente a Namibia. Se comparan las dos especies encontradas con, entre otras, *Neolepton atlanticum* (E. A. Smith, 1890), muy extendida en Sudáfrica, basándonos en nuestro propio material de False Bay.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, *Neolepton*, Veneroidea, SE Atlantic Ocean, SW Africa.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, *Neolepton*, Veneroidea, Océano Atlántico sudoriental, África sudoccidental.

INTRODUCTION

Neoleptonidae Thiele, 1934 is a rather small bivalve family in the superfamily Veneroidea; it currently includes six genera. Only 34 valid taxa are currently given in the type genus *Neolepton* Monterosato, 1875 (MOLLUSCABASE 2024). In this study we introduce two

new species in *Neolepton* from off Namibia, SW Africa.

An important publication on Neoleptonidae is MONTEROSATO (1875) who introduced the genus for the type species *Neolepton sulcatulum* (Jeffreys, 1859) described from Guernsey. SALAS

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& GOFAS (1998) reported on several congeneric species, including five new taxa. They redescribed *N. sulcatulum*, from the English Channel and the Mediterranean Sea, using SEM of shells, critical-point dried soft parts, and semi-thin sections. They introduced a new combination for *Neolepton atlanticum* and analysed material from St. Helena and South Africa. Information was also provided on the species *N. antipodum* (Filhol, 1880) from New Zealand, *N. cobbi* (Cooper & Preston, 1910) from the Falkland Islands and *N. subtrigonum* (Carpenter, 1857) from the Pacific coast of North and South America. Finally, four new species (*N. guanche* from the Canary Is., *N. cancellatum* from the Azores, *N. benguelensis* from Angola, *N. caledonicum* from New Caledonia) were described, and *N. sootryeni* from Tristan da Cunha was renamed. VAN DER LINDEN (2003) introduced five new species from the eastern Atlantic Ocean and the Caribbean Sea. ZELAYA & ITUARTE (2004) described the neoleptonids from southern Chile and the SW Atlantic Ocean; additionally, with three new species. The southernmost occurrence of the genus is on the shores of South Georgia Islands with two species described by ZELAYA & ITUARTE (2003).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material for this study was collected during two cruises of the research vessels Maria S. Merian (MSM105) and Meteor (M122) off the coast of Namibia. Sediment samples were obtained using van Veen grabs, box-corers, gravity-corers and dredges. The sediment samples were sieved by washing, retaining the fractions larger than 1 mm. The residues of MSM105 were fixed in formalin, sorted, and identified in the laboratory.

The shells in the samples from cruise M122 were obtained from thanatocoenoses in seafloor sediments from a gravity core (GeoB20529-1: 20.7245°S,

12.8456°E, 165 m water depth) with a total recovery of 225 cm below seafloor (HEBBELN *ET AL.* 2017). Sieve fractions larger than 0.5 mm were sorted for molluscs.

Undamaged, fresh-looking, large complete shells of *Lucinoma capensis* (Jaeckel & Thiele, 1931) taken from the core at 10 – 12 cm depth were dated to 13.2 ka BP (i.e. the Bölling-Alleröd oscillation, a somewhat less cold interval near the end of the Last Glacial) while the second shell collected at 85 – 87 cm core depth were dated to 42.1 ka BP (also a cool period). Some shells and specimens were colour-photographed using a stereo microscope at IOW while others were prepared for scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging at IOW and SaM. In addition, material of *Neolepton atlanticum* (E. A. Smith, 1890) was used, which was obtained during a sampling campaign in False Bay in 2014 with the help of divers. The campaign was part of the SUBMARINE GROUNDWATER DISCHARGE (SGD) project.

The neoleptonid species typically have two anterior cardinal teeth merged proximally (2a, 2b on the left valve, 3a, 3b on the right valve) which form hook-like structures; in addition the right valve has a median cardinal tooth (1) situated between 3a and 3b. There is one posterior lateral tooth (PII) on the left valve, and two (PI and PIII) on the right valve, the PIII commonly inconspicuous. The terminology used in hinge descriptions follows COX in MOORE (1969: N55-N57), as also did SALAS & GOFAS (1998), and the teeth are labelled on Figures 1-3.

The type material has been deposited at the Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt (SMF), while other reference materials are kept at the IOW.

Abbreviations

SaM – Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven (Germany);
SMF – Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt (Germany);
IOW – Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research, Warnemünde (Germany).

SYSTEMATIC RESULTS

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758
Superfamily VENEROIDEA Rafinesque, 1815
Family NEOLEPTONIDAE Thiele, 1934
Genus *Neolepton* Monterosato, 1875

Type species is *Neolepton sulcatulum* (Jeffreys, 1859), by subsequent designation.

Neolepton torraense n. sp. (Fig. 1)

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Type material (55 valves). *Holotype*: NAMIBIA • 1 valve (Fig. 1D); off Torra Bay; 20.7245°S, 12.8456°E; 165 m water depth; 04 Jan. 2016; M122 sta. GeoB 20529-1; gravity corer in Late Pleistocene; core depth 55–60 cm; in coarse bryozoan fragments with bivalve and gastropod shells; SMF373043. *Paratypes* (54 valves): NAMIBIA • 2 valves; same location as for holotype; core depth 0–10 cm; SMF373044 • 1 valve; same location as for holotype; core depth 10–20 cm; SMF373045 • 13 valves; same location as for holotype; core depth 25–30 cm; SMF373046 • 5 valves; same location as for holotype; core depth 35–40 cm; SMF373047 • 18 valves; same location as for holotype; core depth 45–50 cm; SMF373048 • 2 valves; same location as for holotype; core depth 55–60 cm; SEM; SMF373049 • 11 valves; same location as for holotype; core depth 55–60 cm; SMF373050 • 1 valve; same location as for holotype; core depth 65–70 cm; SMF373051 • 1 valve; same location as for holotype; core depth 105–110 cm; SMF373052.

Type locality: Namibia, off Torra Bay, 20.7245°S, 12.8456°E, 165 m water depth.

Type stratum: Late Pleistocene.

Etymology: *torraense* refers to the nearby Torra Bay and the Torra Conservancy (nature reserve).

Diagnosis: Small fragile shell, equiv-alve, subequilateral, oblong-oval outline with convex margins and pointed umbo inclined anteriorly; moderately inflated. Both valves with one elongated posterior tooth and anterior cardinal teeth below the umbo; oblique triangular ligament pit. Height up to 2.9 mm, length up to 3.3 mm, tumidity of single valve up to 0.9 mm.

Description: Prodissoconch single stage. Outline subcircular, with large elevated circular nucleus; smooth; marked margin demarcating from dissoconch; height 0.24 mm, length 0.26 mm (Fig. 1H).

Dissoconch with postero-dorsal margin nearly straight, slightly convex; antero-dorsal margin mostly convex but concavely raised towards umbo. External sculpture with regular smooth co-marginal growth stages near the umbo, irregular and coarse towards margin (Fig. 1D). Periostracum not seen. No lunule or escutcheon discernable. Shell

internally smooth, thickened between pallial line and margin; pallial line (without sinus) and muscle scars inconspicuous, of equal size; broad pallial margin with glossy shine, blunt smooth shell margin (Figs. 1A, E). Convex posterior hinge plate; concave anterior hinge plate (Figs. 1A, E). Left valve with arc-shaped elongated posterior tooth (PII), one smaller anterior cardinal tooth perpendicular to dorsal margin (2b) and one more marginal larger, oblique cardinal tooth (2a) coming very close to each other in their upper part, see Fig. 1C. Right valve with elongated posterior lateral tooth (PI) projecting in arc shape at the edge of cardinal platform and an inconspicuous PIII closer to the dorsal margin; three divergent cardinals (1, 3a, 3b): the central one (1) large, comma-shaped, oblique, a small anterior cardinal tooth parallel to dorsal margin (3a), joined with the upper end of the tiny 3b to form a hook-shaped structure, see Figure 1G. Oblique, triangular, chon-

Figure 1. *Neolepton torraense* n. sp., Namibia, M122 sta. GeoB 20529-1, gravity core depth 55–60 cm, Late Pleistocene. A-C. Paratype 1, left valve, SMF373049. A, B: internal and umbonal view, height 2.9 mm, length 3.3 mm, tumidity single valve 0.85 mm; C: hinge, anterior cardinal teeth 2a, 2b, posterior lateral tooth PII. D. Holotype, right valve, external view, height 2.6 mm, length 3.0 mm, SMF373043. E-H. Paratype 2, right valve, SMF373049. E, F: internal and umbonal view, height 2.5 mm, length 3.1 mm, tumidity of single valve 0.75 mm; G: hinge, anterior cardinal teeth 1, 3a, 3b, posterior lateral teeth PI, PIII, lig: ligamental pit; H: prodissoconch, height 0.24 mm, length 0.26 mm.

Figura 1. *Neolepton torraense* n. sp., Namibia, estación M122. GeoB 20529-1, testigo de gravedad en profundidad 55–60 cm, Pleistoceno tardío. A-C. Paratipo 1, valva izquierda, SMF373049. A, B: vista interna y umbonal, altura 2,9 mm, longitud 3,3 mm, tumidez en una valva 0,85 mm; C: charnела, dientes cardinales anteriores 2a, 2b, diente lateral posterior PII. D. Holotipo, valva derecha, vista externa, altura 2,6 mm, longitud 3,0 mm, SMF373043. E-H. Paratipo 2, valva derecha, SMF373049. E, F: vista interna y umbonal, altura 2,5 mm, longitud 3,1 mm, tumidez en una valva 0,75 mm; G: charnела, dientes cardinales anteriores 1, 3a, 3b, dientes laterales posteriores PI y PIII, lig: fósula del ligamento; H: prodissoconcha, altura 0,24 mm, longitud 0,26 mm.

Figure 2. *Neolepton atlanticum* (E. A. Smith, 1890), South Africa, False Bay near Gordon's Bay. A: left valve, IOW-ID S7.14, length 2.4 mm; B, C: left and right valves, IOW-ID S37.27, length 2.9 mm; D, E: left valve, IOW-ID S36.43, length 2.1 mm; F: left valve, IOW-ID S36.43, length 2.1 mm; G, H: right valve, IOW-ID S36.43, length 1.9 mm; I: shell, umbonal view, IOW-ID S37.27, length 1.9 mm, tumidity 0.9 mm; J: detail of umbonal area showing prodissoconch, length 0.22 mm. Numbering of hinge teeth as for Figure 1; lig: ligament or ligamental pit.

Figura 2. Neolepton atlanticum (E. A. Smith, 1890), Sudáfrica, False Bay cerca de Gordon's Bay. A: valva izquierda, IOW-ID S7.14, longitud 2,4 mm; B, C: valvas izquierda y derecha, IOW-ID S37.27, longitud 2,9 mm; D, E: valva izquierda, IOW-ID S36.43, longitud 2,1 mm; F: valva izquierda, IOW-ID S36.43, longitud 2,1 mm; G, H: valva derecha, IOW-ID S36.43, longitud 1,9 mm; I: concha, vista umbonal, IOW-ID S37.27, longitud 1,9 mm, tumidez 0,9 mm; J: detalle de la zona del umbo mostrando la prodissoconcha, longitud 0,22 mm. Numeración de los dientes de la charnela como en la Figura 1; lig: ligamento o fósula del ligamento.

drophore with resilifer anteriorly below umbo.

Variability: Minor differences have been observed regarding the height to length ratio of the valves in the type set: 0.8–0.9. The ratio of the tumidity of one valve and its length is about 0.25.

Differential diagnosis: The type species *Neolepton sulcatulum* from the eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea is smaller (length 1.5 mm), subcircular, subequilateral, it has clear lateral teeth and it has fine co-marginal growth margins (SALAS & GOFAS, 1998: 40–41, figs 1–17). The present species has a similar prodissoconch and hinge but it is much larger (length 3 mm), with oblong-oval outline, weak lateral teeth and very weak co-marginal sculpture. All eastern Atlantic species show a distinct co-marginal sculpture, some of them also a radial sculpture, and they are smaller with typically less than 2 mm in length (SALAS & GOFAS 1998, VAN DER LINDEN, 2003). *Neolepton caledonicum* Salas & Gofas, 1998 from off New Caledonia, western Pacific and *Neolepton atlanticum* (Smith, 1890) from off St. Helena and South Africa, southern Atlantic both have a similar outline, size (length up to 3 mm) and hinge but they both have a distinct, yet fine, co-marginal sculpture, a very weak posterior tooth in the left

valve and a smaller prodissoconch (length 0.22 mm, Fig. 2J), (SALAS & GOFAS 1998: 47–52, figs 2A-E; Fig. 2 herein). The present species only has a weak co-marginal sculpture, posterior teeth PI and PII of equal strength in both valves and a larger prodissoconch (length 0.26 mm, Fig. 1H). *Neolepton cobbi* (Cooper & Preston, 1910) from the Falkland Islands and *N. concentricum* (Preston, 1910) have a subcircular outline and strong co-marginal sculpture (ZELAYA & ITUARTE 2004: 123–129, figs 1–7). *Neolepton hupei* Soot-Ryen, 1957 from southern Chile, Terra del Fuego and the Falkland Islands and *N. yagan* Zelaya & Ituarte, 2004 from Terra del Fuego and southern Chile have a similar prodissoconch, hinge and weak sculpture but show highly convex anterior margins and broadly rounded posterior margin. The former species is much larger (length 5.4 mm) and the latter is smaller (2.4 mm) than the present species (3 mm) (ZELAYA & ITUARTE 2004: 129, 131, 133, figs 8, 11). Furthermore, the present species has a more oblong outline.

Remarks: All findings from Namibia were made in Late Pleistocene sediment dominated by fragments of erect bryozoan colonies and shell fragments. The species is only known from the type material.

Neolepton san n. sp. (Fig. 3)

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Type material (9 specimens). *Holotype:* NAMIBIA • 1 live-collected specimen; MSM105 sta. 88; 27.000°S, 14.083°E; 419 m; 03 Feb. 2022; van Veen grab; SMF373053. *Paratypes:* NAMIBIA • 3 live-collected specimens; same location data as holotype; SMF373054 • 3 live-collected specimens; MSM105 sta. 85; 27.000°S, 14.817°E; 785 m; 03 Feb. 2022; box corer; SMF373055 • 2 live-collected specimens; MSM105 sta. 89; 27.000°S, 14.267°E; 383 m; 03 Feb. 2022; van Veen grab; SMF373056.

Other material investigated (5 specimens): NAMIBIA • 1 live-collected specimen; MSM105 sta. 6; 23.000°S, 12.783°E; 940 m; 13 Jan. 2022; box corer; IOW. • 2 live-collected specimens; MSM105 sta. 12; 23.000°S, 13.317°E; 360 m; 14 Jan. 2022; van Veen grab; IOW • 2 live-collected specimens; MSM105 sta. 84; 27.000°S, 13.717°E; 1032 m; 02 Feb. 2022; box corer; IOW.

Type locality: Namibia, 27.000°S, 14.083°E, 419 m water depth.

Etymology: *san* (noun) refers to the language of the indigenous people San.

Diagnosis: Small oval shell, equivalve, subequilateral. Colour white with light translucent yellowish periostracum.

Outline convex on anterior, posterior and ventral margins, pointed at umbo, inclined anteriorly, flattened dorsal margins (Figs

Figure 3. *Neolepton san* n. sp., holotype, MSM105-88, Namibia2022, SMF373053. A, B, E, G. Left valve. C, D, H. Right valve. A: external view, height 2.4 mm, length 2.9 mm; B: internal view; C: external view; D: internal view; E: prodissoconch, length 0.50 mm; F: umbonal view of complete shell, tumidity (2 valves) 1.4 mm; G: hinge, anterior cardinal teeth 2a, 2b, posterior lateral tooth PII; H: hinge, anterior cardinal teeth 1, 3a, 3b, posterior lateral teeth PI and PIII; lig: ligament or ligamental pit.

Figura 3. Neolepton san n. sp., holotipo, MSM105-88, Namibia2022, SMF373053. A, B, E, G. Valva izquierda. C, D, H. Valva derecha. A: vista externa, altura 2,4 mm, longitud 2,9 mm; B: vista interna; C: vista externa; D: vista interna; E: prodissoconcha, longitud 0,50 mm; F: vista umbonal de la concha completa, tumidez (2 valvas) 1,4 mm; G: charnela, dientes cardinales anteriores 2a, 2b, diente lateral posterior PII; H: charnela, dientes cardinales anteriores 1, 3a, 3b, dientes laterales posteriores PI y PIII; lig: ligamento o fósula del ligamento.

3A-D). Both valves with posterior lateral teeth and anterior cardinal teeth below the umbo, the anterior cardinal 2a of left valve strongly bulging; very large oblique triangular ligament pit (Figs 3G-H). Height 2.4 mm, length 2.9 mm, tumidity 1.4 mm (2 valves).

Description: Prodissoconch mostly eroded; oval-oblong, smooth; margin with thin rim, length 0.50 mm. Dissoconch: exterior smooth with fine growth lines. Internally smooth with clear pallial line and muscle scars (Figs 3B, D). Hinge with very large central internal resilium. Left valve with two merged anterior cardinal teeth (2a and 2b), of which the 2a is strongly widened and bulging towards its anterior end; one elongated oblique posterior tooth (PII), see Fig. 3G. Right valve with a thick, oblique and relatively short posterior lateral tooth (PI) and an inconspicuous PIII above it, three divergent cardinals (1, 3a, 3b): the central one (1) thick, triangular and prominent, very oblique; small anterior cardinal tooth (3a) parallel to dorsal margin, joined with the upper end of the tiny 3b to form a hook-shaped structure.

Variability: Minor differences have been observed in the type set.

Differential diagnosis: Refer to the differential diagnosis for *Neolepton torraense*

n. sp. for differences between the present species and other eastern Atlantic species, including the smaller type species. Both new species have a very weak co-marginal sculpture and they lack a radial sculpture whereas all other eastern Atlantic species show a clear and regular co-marginal sculpture, often with fine radial ridges and with outlines that are more subcircular, not elongated. *Neolepton torraense* n. sp. has an oblong-oval outline and has long posterior teeth. The present species has a distinct elongated-oval outline and unusually short posterior teeth. *Neolepton hupei* Soot-Ryen, 1957 and *N. yagan* Zelaya & Ituarte, 2004 from the SW Atlantic and southern Chile have a similar prodissoconch, hinge, weak sculpture and convex anterior margin and broadly rounded posterior margin. The former species is much larger (length 5.4 mm) and the latter is smaller (2.4 mm) than the present species (2.9 mm) (ZELAYA & ITUARTE 2004: 129, 131, 133, figs 8, 11). Furthermore, the present species has a more elongated outline.

Remarks: The present species is only known from the material reported herein in a latitudinal range 23 – 27 °S off Namibia and in a bathymetric depth range 370 – 1032 m.

DISCUSSION

The two new species of Neoleptonidae described here from Namibia close a gap in the description of the SW African neoleptonid fauna. Different congeneric species are known from South Africa (*Neolepton atlanticum* (E. A. Smith, 1890)) and Angola (*Neolepton benguelensis* Salas & Gofas, 1998). In view of the relatively recent additions to the family from western Africa and eastern South America it is likely that more species will be discovered in the southern Atlantic Ocean.

Neolepton torraense n. sp. was found on the continental shelf in a Late Pleistocene sequence. Most likely it lived epibenthically in shallow waters, possibly with sympatric erect bryozoan

species. *Neolepton san* n. sp. lives deeper, on the upper bathyal slope.

The type species and most other species of the genus live intertidally or in the shallow sublittoral (SALAS & GOFAS 1998; VAN DER LINDEN 2003; ZELAYA & ITUARTE 2004; COAN & VALENTICH-SCOTT 2012). One of the few exceptions is *N. hupei*, which has also been recorded down to a water depth of 286 metres (ZELAYA & ITUARTE 2004). Another is *N. profundorum* Allen, 2000, which has been described at water depths between 1011 and 2323 metres (ALLEN, 2000). The recent species found in this study, *Neolepton san* n. sp., was found in water depths between 360 and 1032 m, and is thus only the second

known *Neolepton* species found in upper bathyal water depths.

Neoleptonidae were placed in Veneroidea following morphological study by SALAS & GOFAS (1998). Even though the genus *Neolepton* and most of its sister taxa seem well defined by the morphological features of their shells and soft parts, a classification of the family and its genera would benefit from molecular analyses.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The crews and scientific staffs of the cruises MSM105 and M122 are thanked for their dedication during the sediment sampling. The cruises were sponsored by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. MSM105 was part of the EVAR project

funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (grant no. 03V01279). Frank Pohl and Mayya Gogina (Rostock) provided assistance to the second author during MSM105. André Freiwald, the Head of the Marine Research Department at Senckenberg am Meer in Wilhelmshaven, granted access to the M122 material and laboratory facilities. Claudia Wienberg from MARUM, University of Bremen, provided access to the gravity core M122 GeoB 20529 and coordinated critical analytical matters, such as core sampling and sieving, and ¹⁴C dating. We are particularly grateful to an anonymous reviewer who corrected our previous taxonomic classification. The SUBMARINE GROUNDWATER DISCHARGE (SGD) project was funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (grant no. 02WSP1306C).

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